

Comparison Analysis of Random Forest and Naïve Bayes Algorithms for Rainfall Classification Based on Climate in Indonesia

Nicolaus Advendea Prakoso Indaryono^{1✉}, Rd. Rohmat Saedudin², Faqih Hamami³

¹ Telkom University, Indonesia

² Telkom University, Indonesia

³ Telkom University, Indonesia

⁴ Telkom University, Indonesia

Abstract

Indonesia predominantly features a tropical climate across its entirety. With this mostly tropical climate, the country encounters minimal shifts in temperature but exhibits a wide array of rainfall variations. Rainfall patterns in Indonesia showcase significant diversity. These variations in rainfall hold substantial importance in mitigating risks linked to heavy rainfall, such as floods and landslides. Moreover, besides its role in disaster preparedness, rainfall data also holds practical value in sectors such as agriculture, transportation, and industry. By incorporating data mining classification techniques, the process of predicting rainfall in Indonesia can be greatly enhanced. In this study, daily climate data from Indonesia is harnessed, and the chosen method for classification is the random forest algorithm. This selection stems from its capability to generate accurate and consistent classification models without necessitating intricate adjustments of parameters. Furthermore, the Naïve Bayes method is also integrated due to its straightforward implementation and its capacity for simple probability modeling, which can be effectively applied across diverse classification data. The outcomes of this investigation suggest that the random forest algorithm surpasses the Naïve Bayes algorithm in terms of performance and accuracy when classifying climate datasets unique to Indonesia. The random forest algorithm attains an accuracy rate of 86.55%, whereas the Naïve Bayes algorithm lags at an accuracy rate of 36.61%. It is anticipated that these research findings can serve as a point of reference for subsequent scholarly inquiries and contribute to the ongoing monitoring of daily rainfall in Indonesia, thereby aiding in the prevention of natural disasters.

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Corresponding Author :

Nicolaus Advendea Prakoso Indaryono

Telkom University, Indonesia

Jl. Telekomunikasi. 1, Terusan Buahbatu - Bojongsoang, Telkom University, Sukapura, Kec.

Dayeuhkolot, Kabupaten Bandung, Jawa Barat 40257

Email : rdohmat@telkomuniversity.ac.id

INTRODUCTION

The continuous increase in urban population, which is becoming denser or larger and reaching up to 20 million inhabitants in some major cities, makes cities highly vulnerable to the dangers of climate change. Atmospheric warming leads to increased rainfall degradation, air pollution, and water issues [1]. Indonesia is a region that is predominantly characterized by a tropical climate. Climate change itself has an impact on the changes in average air temperature anomalies in Indonesia. According to Molle & Larasati, being a region mostly endowed with a tropical climate, Indonesia experiences narrow temperature variations but diverse variations in rainfall patterns. The climate changes occurring also have the potential to result in alterations in rainfall patterns [2]. Rainfall is the total amount of precipitation that occurs in a specific area, assessed on daily, weekly, monthly, and yearly scales, influenced by additional factors, and constituting one of the components of the climate. In Indonesia, rainfall exhibits a significant

level of diversity and is of utmost importance in human life, being interconnected with conditions such as humidity, pressure, temperature, wind direction, and wind speed [3]. Given the high intensity of rainfall in the Indonesian region, there is a need for supporting knowledge to prevent the hazards resulting from disasters caused by high rainfall, such as floods and landslides. Based on data collected by the National Disaster Management Agency (BNPB), there were a total of 2,342 disaster incidents in Indonesia in the year 2016. Among these incidents, 92% were primarily hydrometeorological disasters like floods, landslides, and tornadoes. Specifically, there were 766 flood incidents, 612 landslide incidents, and 74 combined flood and landslide incidents. The high levels of rainfall in the affected areas were the main cause of these floods and landslides. These tragedies had severe consequences that cannot be overlooked. The impacts of these natural disasters led to loss of life, health issues, home damage, and destruction of public buildings. Around 3.05 million people were displaced and suffered, 522 lives were lost, 69,287 houses were damaged, and 2,311 public buildings were destroyed [4]. In addition to preparing for the resulting disasters, information regarding rainfall can also be utilized for various purposes such as in the fields of agriculture, transportation, and industry. Hence, techniques are required to classify rainfall. One of the methods that can be employed for data analysis and processing, benefiting the readers, is the data mining method. According to Jackson, data mining is the process of identifying and generating useful and understandable data patterns and correlations. The overall process of data mining is referred to as Knowledge Discovery in Databases (KDD). KDD consists of several process stages such as preparation, selection, cleaning, and interpretation of the results from the data mining process [5]. By sifting through the amassed data, data mining is the process of discovering new connections, patterns, and valuable trends. To extract information from extensive datasets, the multidisciplinary field of data mining combines methods from machine learning, pattern recognition, statistics, databases, and visualization [6]. On the other hand, according to Jollyta et al., data mining is a method that employs artificial intelligence, statistics, and arithmetic to unveil new knowledge from large amounts of data within a database. Data mining is a technique that can bridge consumer demands with data needs [7]. In its application, data mining encompasses several algorithmic models that can be implemented, including the random forest and naïve Bayes algorithms. Random forest is a classification algorithm belonging to the ensemble category. This algorithm constructs a forest composed of multiple decision trees. During classification, the random forest employs a voting technique to make decisions based on all the decision trees. By utilizing numerous decision trees, the random forest algorithm addresses issues that arise when using just a single decision tree for classification. This enhances the overall accuracy and optimizes the classification outcomes [8]. On the other hand, the naïve bayes method is a classification technique grounded in probability and statistical approaches, devised by a British scientist named Thomas Bayes. The objective of this algorithm is to predict future outcomes based on past results, hence named the Bayes Theorem. This theory is then combined with the term "naïve," which assumes a situation where each attribute is independent of the others [9]. In the study [10] titled "Comparison of Random Forest and Naïve Bayes Methods in Predicting Client Success in Telemarketing," which focuses on predicting client decisions to assist telemarketing performance, the comparison results of the naïve Bayes and random forest algorithms showed an accuracy of 85% for naïve Bayes and 90% for random forest. Based on these findings, it can be concluded that in the research conducted for predicting telemarketing client success, the random forest algorithm performs better in this classification task. Furthermore, in another study [11] involving the classification of debtors based on credit quality, an accuracy of 98.16% was achieved using the random forest algorithm compared to 95.93% with the naïve Bayes algorithm. Previous research has consistently demonstrated that the random forest algorithm is superior in performing classification tasks. In this study, the author aims to compare the performance of the Random Forest and Naïve Bayes algorithms in classifying rainfall based on climate data from various regions across Indonesia. Additionally, an analysis of the comparison between the utilization of the random forest and naïve Bayes algorithmic methods will be conducted, utilizing daily climate data from Indonesia to classify rainfall patterns.

RESEARCH METHOD

Data Mining

Data mining is the practice of automatically analyzing and extracting knowledge from data using one or more machine learning algorithms. This interactive and iterative process searches for new patterns or models that are relevant, practical, and understandable within large databases. In data mining, the quest is to uncover desired trends or patterns within extensive datasets to aid future decision-making. Specialized tools providing meaningful and insightful data analysis can identify these patterns, which can then be further investigated with the assistance of other decision-making aids if necessary [12].

Classification Method

Classification is one of the approaches for implementing data mining. This method is a data analysis technique that generates models identifying significant primary data types. These models, referred to as classifiers, can be employed to predict the membership of data into predetermined classes [13].

Random Forest

Random forest is an algorithm developed by Leo Breiman. It is a collection of regression or classification trees that are unpruned and constructed by selecting random samples from the data. Predictions are made by combining the prediction results from all the individual regression or classification trees within the collection. Random forest offers advantages such as the ability to detect relatively large errors, good classification performance, capability to handle datasets with a small number of samples, and effectiveness in estimating missing data [14].

Naïve Bayes

The Naïve Bayes probabilistic categorization technique determines the overall probability by incrementing the frequency and considering the available information. The algorithm, based on the Bayes concept, illustrates how all qualities are determined by the class variable and are not independent or unrelated to each other. Naive Bayes can be utilized as it employs a small amount of training data to reliably predict classification-related parameters. In real-world conditions that are more intricate than anticipated, the naive approach often outperforms predictions [15].

SMOTE (Synthetic Minority Oversampling Technique)

The SMOTE approach employs the concept of oversampling, which involves adding unbalanced or insufficient class data to balance the figures with data from the majority class. This method will utilize neighborhood techniques to generate data from the minority class [16].

Confusion Matrix

Data mining employs the Confusion Matrix to determine the accuracy of model predictions. The matrix, utilized to determine values such as accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-Score, comprises data about the number of accurate or inaccurate predictions. The fraction of correctly projected positive instances based on actual data is termed precision. The percentage of actual occurrences correctly anticipated as positive is known as recall, also referred to as sensitivity [17-22].

Data Identification

In the data identification phase, an understanding and analysis of the acquired dataset are conducted to filter and select relevant attributes. The selected attributes will be involved in the classification process. The selection of attributes is based on factors that can influence rainfall. Following the data identification process, the next step is to determine the variables to be used for the research, dividing them into two types: independent variables and dependent variables, as shown in Table 1.

Tabel 1. Research Variables

Variable	Nama	Definition
Independent Variables (X)	Tavg	Average temperature (
	RH_avg	Average humidity (%)

	ss	Duration of sunlight (hour)
	Ddd_x	Wind direction with maximum speed (deg)
Dependent Variables (Y)	RR	Rainfall (mm) categories :
		0 = light
		1 = moderate
		2 = heavy
		3 = very heavy

Data Preprocessing

After determining the attributes to be used, the process of identifying empty data is undertaken. This is addressed by finding interpolation values for attributes that have null values. Replacing null values with interpolation values is chosen because the dataset exhibits changing values following a pattern over time. Hence, the method of substituting null values with interpolation values can be a suitable choice, replacing the missing values with the existing climate data trends.

After addressing the absence of empty data, the process of labeling the dataset to be used is carried out. The attributes of the data that will be labeled in the dataset for the classification process are the rainfall categories based on the probabilistic rainfall classification by BMKG.

Tabel 2. Research Categories

Range	Label	Rainfall Category
0.5 – 20	1	Light
20 – 50	2	Moderate
50 – 100	2	Heavy
>100	3	Very Heavy

After conducting the categorization process on the dataset, the labeled data can be seen in Table 5.

Tabel 3. Data Labeling

Tavg	RH_avg	ss	Dddx	Label	category
27.2	86.0	8.0	180.0	1.0	Light
27.2	86.0	6.0	80.0	1.0	Light
26.5	88.0	8.5	130.0	1.0	Light
27.2	88.0	1.0	130.0	1.0	Light
26.9	88.0	3.0	100.0	1.0	Light

Based on the labeling results, the number of labels in each class is as follows

Tabel 4. Number of Labels

Class	Total
0	86.55%
1	86.25%
2	86.25%
3	86.5%
Total	31.754

After obtaining the labeled data results, an imbalance in the number of instances was observed in each class, as depicted in Figure 1. To address the imbalanced data in each class, the SMOTE method was employed to perform oversampling or generate synthetic data for the

underrepresented classes within the climate dataset in Indonesia. The outcome of data augmentation using the SMOTE method is presented.

Gambar 1. Data before and after smote

Modeling and Evaluation

In this phase, the classification process is carried out by implementing the selected algorithms, namely naïve Bayes, and random forest. The testing phase is divided into two parts: training data and testing data, with an 80:20 split ratio. The tool used for classification is Google Colab, employing the Python programming language. Following the modeling phase of both algorithms, the evaluation process is conducted, comparing the algorithms using the Confusion Matrix method. The evaluation phase will also yield accuracy, F1- Score, precision, and recall values, as well as display the optimal ROC curve and AUC for each tested classification algorithm.

MinMax Scaler Normalization

The MinMax Scaler process aims to reduce the required computational effort. Through this approach, it is expected that accuracy will increase, and the time needed for the training process will be reduced. Min-Max is used to transform the value range of each variable so that the values are between 0 and 1.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Algorithm Comparison

In testing the dataset using the Naïve Bayes and Random Forest algorithms, the respective algorithmic model functions were employed through the importation of the sklearn library in Python. The research utilized an 80:20 ratio. The conducted study produced the confusion matrix values for each compared algorithm. Subsequently, from the comparison of the confusion matrix outcomes, Recall, Precision, F1-Score, and AUC scores were obtained. The comparative results of the Naïve Bayes and Random Forest algorithms can be observed in the following table.

Tabel 5. Algorithm Comparison

	Naïve Bayes	Random Forest
Accuracy	36.61%	86.55%
Precision	33.25%	86.25%
Recall	36.75%	86.25%
F1-Score	30.25%	86.5%
AUC Score	61.75%	97%

and the AUC score graph of the Naïve Bayes algorithm can be seen in Figure 3, while the AUC score graph of the Random Forest algorithm can be seen in Figure 4.

Gambar 2. AUC score naive bayes

Gambar 3. AUC score random forest

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

Conclusion

The evaluation results of comparing the Naïve Bayes and Random Forest algorithms yielded the following outcomes. For the Naïve Bayes algorithm, an accuracy of 36.61% was obtained, with an average Precision of 33.25%, average Recall of 36.75%, average F1-Score of 30.25%, and an average AUC Score of 61.75%, falling into the category of very poor AUC scores. On the other hand, for the Random Forest algorithm, an accuracy of 86.55% was achieved, with an average Precision of 86.25%, average Recall of 86.25%, average F1-Score of 86.5%, and an average AUC Score of 97%, categorized as a very good AUC score. Based on these results, it can be concluded that the Random Forest algorithm outperforms the Naïve Bayes algorithm in terms of accuracy, precision, recall, F1-Score, and AUC score comparisons.

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